

AudRandAug: Random Image Augmentations for Audio Classification

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Abstract

Data augmentation has proven to be effective in training neural networks. Recently, a method called RandAug was proposed, randomly selecting data augmentation techniques from a predefined search space. RandAug has demonstrated significant performance improvements for image-related tasks while imposing minimal computational overhead. However, no prior research has explored the application of RandAug specifically for audio data augmentation, which converts audio into an image-like pattern. To address this gap, we introduce AudRandAug, an adaptation of RandAug for audio data. AudRandAug selects data augmentation policies from a dedicated audio search space. To evaluate the effectiveness of AudRandAug, we conducted experiments using various models and datasets. Our findings indicate that AudRandAug outperforms other existing data augmentation methods regarding accuracy performance.

Keywords: Audio Classification, Data Augmentation, Random Audio Augmentation

1 Introduction

Deep learning (DL) has successfully addressed complex problems, proving proficiency in managing large datasets and discerning intricate patterns. Consequently, DL has become an indispensable tool for various tasks, including image recognition [Aleem et al., 2022, Wu and Chen, 2015, Fujiyoshi et al., 2019, Kumar et al., 2021a, Kumar et al., 2023b, Kumar et al., 2023a, Ranjbarzadeh et al., 2023], natural language processing [Torfi et al., 2020, Hirschberg and Manning, 2015, ?], and audio processing [Hershey et al., 2017, Fu et al., 2010, Turab et al., 2022, Park et al., 2020, Chandio et al., 2021]. Notably, DL has demonstrated impressive performance in the field of audio data analysis. Extensive research has been conducted on numerous tasks such as audio classification, music generation, and environmental sound classification [Lee et al., 2017b].

Previous studies [Fu et al., 2010, Turab et al., 2022, Park et al., 2020, Kumar et al., 2020] have highlighted the challenge of training neural networks directly on raw audio data, as it can be difficult for them to learn essential features. To overcome this limitation, researchers have shown that neural networks can achieve significantly improved performance by training them on audio-specific features [Palanisamy et al., 2020]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been widely employed for audio content analysis, utilizing various features and methods [Turab et al., 2022, Palanisamy et al., 2020, Li et al., 2019].

Despite the accuracy achieved through feature extraction methods, there remains room for improvement due to limited availability of labeled data. Deep learning models require large-scale labeled data to learn more accurate features. However, the process of labeling data on a large scale is tedious, time-consuming, and expensive [Kumar et al., 2021b]. To address this challenge, various data augmentation (DA) techniques can be applied to existing data by increasing the diversity and size of data, allowing the model to learn from different

perspectives of each sample. The objective is to train the network on additional distorted data, enabling the network to become invariant to these distortions and generalize better to unseen data. Several studies have explored data augmentation methods in the audio domain [Ko et al., 2015, Nanni et al., 2020, Jain et al., 2021]. In line with the principles of image randAug [Cubuk et al., 2020], we propose a novel approach for audio classification called AudRandAug, which is demonstrated in Figure 1. Our work contributes in the following ways:

- Inspired by RandAug, we introduce a novel data augmentation technique named AudRandAug.
- We perform several experiment to select the most effective augmentation methods for inclusion in the search space of AudRandAug
- To validate the proposed approach, we perform several experiments on different datasets.
- We provide code in GitHub repository: <https://github.com/turab45/AudRandAug.git>

The rest of the paper is organized as, section 2 discusses the related work, section 3 explains the proposed methodology, section 4 provides experimental details such as datasets, training setup and results, and finally section 6 concludes the work.

2 Related Work

This section discusses relevant data augmentation work in the audio domain. Deep learning methods have been widely applied to audio/sound data, such as music genre classification [Dong, 2018, Choi et al., 2017, Zhang et al., 2016], audio generation [Oord et al., 2016, Roberts et al., 2018], environmental sound classification [Guzhov et al., 2021, Aytar et al., 2016, Demir et al., 2020], and more [Chachada and Kuo, 2014, Dandashi and AlJaam, 2017]. From an architectural perspective, various methods have been explored for audio classification. Models using 1-D Convolution, such as EnvNet [Tokozume and Harada, 2017] and Sample-CNN [Lee et al., 2017b], have been proposed for raw audio waveform classification. However, recent work has primarily focused on utilizing CNN on spectrogram (an image pattern), which has led to state-of-the-art (SOTA) results. Dong et al. [Dong, 2018] proposed a CNN-based method for music genre classification, and Palanisamy et al. [Palanisamy et al., 2020] showed that an ImageNet pre-trained model could be a strong baseline network for audio classification.

In addition to architectural considerations, data augmentation has shown promising results in various audio tasks. For convenience, audio data augmentation can be broadly divided into two levels: (i) data augmentation on the raw audio level and (ii) data augmentation on the feature level.

2.1 Data augmentation on raw audio level

Extensive research has been carried out on using deep learning techniques for raw audio data analysis. Various models have been developed specifically for classifying raw audio waveforms using 1-D Convolutions. For instance, EnvNet [Tokozume and Harada, 2017] and Sample-CNN [Lee et al., 2017b] are notable examples of models that leverage raw audio waveforms as their inputs. These models have demonstrated significant advancements in achieving SOTA performance across different sound categories [Lee et al., 2017a].

2.2 Data augmentation on features level

Recent research has emphasized employing CNNs on spectrograms to achieve SOTA outcomes. Dong et al. [Dong, 2018] proposed a CNN-based method for music genre classification, achieving accuracy of 70%. Additionally, Palanisamy et al. [Palanisamy et al., 2020] demonstrated that a pre-trained ImageNet model can serve as a strong baseline network for audio classification. To further enhance generalization, a few studies have explored feature extraction [Turab et al., 2022, Su et al., 2019, Liu et al., 1998] and data augmentation

Figure 1: **Example audio mel-spectrograms augmented by AudRandAug.** In these examples, $N = 2$ and different M magnitude values are shown. As the magnitude of the distortion rises, so does the strength of the augmentation.

approaches [Ko et al., 2015, Nanni et al., 2020, Kim et al., 2021]. In the work by Turab et al., [Turab et al., 2022], different feature selection methods were investigated for audio using ensemble techniques. The search for optimal augmentation policies was explored in [BSG, 2020], while Kumar et al. [Kumar et al., 2020] proposed a novel intra-class random erasing data augmentation to enhance network robustness. Furthermore, Kim et al. [Kim et al., 2021] introduced Specmix, a novel audio data augmentation technique specifically designed for time-frequency domain features. This approach improved the performance of various neural network architectures by up to 2.7%. Salamon et al. [Salamon and Bello, 2017] proposed a deep neural network architecture coupled with audio augmentations to address the challenge of data scarcity in their work. Among all these approach, none has explored image randAugment approach for audio data. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to explore it.

3 Proposed Methodology

In this section, we explain the proposed method and used data augmentation methods in the search space.

3.1 Method

Inspired by the RandAug [Cubuk et al., 2020] in the domain of images, we introduce a random data augmentation technique for audio classification called AudRandAug. This approach involves determining the optimal parameters for each specific data augmentation operation. Subsequently, we apply a total of N data augmentations, each with its corresponding optimal magnitude or parameter(s), like an optimal magnitude for time stretch augmentation is 1.4. The proposed algorithm is provided in **algorithm 1**.

Require: N (Integer), M (List)

Ensure: Selected augmentations and magnitudes

- 1: augmentations \leftarrow ["Noise", "Pitch", "Time", "Padding", "Clip", "Trim", "Reverse", "BPF", "BSF"]
- 2: selected_augmentations \leftarrow random choice from augmentations, size N
- 3: selected_magnitude $\leftarrow M$ where selected_augmentation equals augmentation
- 4: **return** [(aug, m) for (m, aug) in zip(selected_magnitude, selected_augmentations)] where m is magnitude of particular augmentation

Algorithm 1: AudRandAug

In our proposed approach, we adopt the same algorithm as described in RandAug [Cubuk et al., 2020]. The selection of data augmentation from the search space is performed with a uniform probability. We investigate several essential audio data augmentations, keeping in mind that all augmentations are applied to audio waveforms and subsequently converted into Mel-spectrograms. Finally, these augmented spectrograms are used as inputs to the CNN model. Table 1 provides a detailed overview of each used data augmentation technique.

Augmentation	Description
Noise Injection	This involves introducing additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) to the original audio recording through element-wise addition.
Pitch Shifting	This alters the pitch of an audio recording without impacting its duration or timing
Time Stretching	This modifies the speed or duration of an audio recording while preserving its pitch and tonal characteristics. This is achieved by utilizing the Short-time Fourier transform (STFT) technique.
Padding	Padding in audio refers to the technique of enhancing the sound quality of a recording by replacing a fraction of the beginning or end of the audio with padded sections.
Clip	Clipping removes excessive audio signal to prevent distortion and ensure a clean sound.
Reverse	Reversing an audio signal involves inverting its polarity, commonly used to create a reversed playback effect or special audio effects.
Band Pass Filter	A band pass filter is an electronic filter designed to permit a specific range of frequencies to pass through while attenuating all others. This filter is frequently employed in audio applications to eliminate unwanted noise and interference, ensuring optimal sound quality.
Gain	To enhance the model’s resilience to variations in input gain, it is beneficial to multiply the audio by a random amplitude factor. By doing so, the model becomes less dependent on specific gain values and exhibits more consistent performance across a diverse range of input signals.
Time Masking	This is an audio technique where a randomly selected portion of the audio is made silent, effectively removing unwanted noises or creating unique effects. This method is commonly employed to enhance audio quality and achieve specific audio effects

Table 1: All the used data augmentation methods

4 Experiment Design

In this section, we explain the training setup, dataset, and results.

4.1 Training Set up

We used custom CNN and pre-trained VGG model, 0.001 learning rate, Adam optimizer, 100 epoch. The custom CNN is 2 convolutional layers network. First convolutional layer followed by max pooling, drop with 0.2. Second convolutional layer is followed by max pooling then flatten. Then two dense layers are used.

4.2 Datasets

We use Free Spoken Digits Dataset (FSDD) [Jackson, 2016] which is a simple audio dataset consisting of English spoken digit recordings in .wav files at 8khz. It contains 3,000 recordings from 6 speakers (50 of each digit per speaker) and English pronunciations, and it has 10 classes (0-9) and duration of the recordings is 1-2 seconds. Another dataset UrbanSound8K dataset [Salamon et al., 2014] contains 8732 labeled urban sound recordings in .wav format. All recordings are of a duration of 4 seconds from 10 classes. The files are sorted by 10 folds (folders called fold1-fold10)

Custom CNN Model Results				
Augmentation	FSDD dataset		UrbanSound8K dataset	
	Performance	Change (ΔD)	Performance	Change (ΔD)
Baseline	92.00	-	95.00	-
+ Noise Injection	94.5	2.5	97.27	2.27
+ Pitch Shifting	94.83	2.83	97.26	2.26
+ Time Stretching	92.50	0.5	97.23	2.23
+ Padding	92.50	0.5	97.13	2.13
+ Clip	93.33	1.33	93.11	1.89
+ Reverse	93.83	1.83	93.13	1.87
+ Band Pass Filter	93.00	1.0	97.31	2.31
+ Gain	96.50	4.5	97.32	2.32
+ Time Mask	92.16	0.16	96.56	1.56
+ Ours	97.16	5.16	96.37	1.37
VGG Model Results				
Baseline	95.95	-	96.37	-
+ Noise Injection	98.16	2.15	97.89	1.52
+ Pitch Shifting	98.66	2.71	98.19	1.82
+ Time Stretching	94.18	1.77	91.17	5.2
+ Padding	93.87	2.39	98.34	1.97
+ Clip	98.66	2.71	98.42	2.05
+ Reverse	93.83	2.12	95.92	0.45
+ Band Pass Filter	93.00	2.95	98.25	1.88
+ Gain	98.66	2.71	97.09	0.72
+ Time Mask	94.39	1.56	97.11	0.74
+ Ours	98.92	2.97	98.63	2.26

Table 2: Result using custom CNN and Pre-trained VGG models

4.3 Pre-processing

First, we apply augmentation on signal level, as the mentioned augmentation methods perform better on signal level rather than mel-spectrogram. We resize the mel-spectrogram to 32 x 32 as an image-like feature before feeding to the network. RandAug applied before training as a data preprocessing step.

5 Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed approach, we conducted experiments using various models on two datasets: FSDD and UrbanSound8K. It is important to note we included all the techniques in the search space that perform better than the baseline. We present the experimental results in Table 2, where a custom CNN was used as the baseline for both datasets. Accuracy served as the evaluation metric. The table reports the difference between each data augmentation (DA) technique and the baseline accuracy, denoted as ΔD . A green ΔD indicates an improvement in accuracy compared to the baseline, while a red ΔD signifies a decrease. Only the data augmentation techniques that demonstrated improved accuracy are included in the table.

Our proposed data augmentation technique using custom CNN exhibited a significant absolute improvement of 5.16% on the FSDD dataset and 1.37% on the UrbanSound8K dataset. The 5.16% absolute improvement over the baseline on the FSDD dataset is particularly noteworthy, as it represents the highest accuracy perfor-

mance among all the utilized DAs. Although the 1.37% improvement on the UrbanSound8K dataset is not the highest, it still demonstrates a competitive enhancement in accuracy.

For the pre-trained VGG model, we conducted a similar set of experiments as with the CNN model. However, we observed that fewer data augmentation methods showed improved performance compared to the CNN case. Therefore, we excluded those augmentations with lower accuracy performance compared to the baseline from the search space. Our proposed method exhibited superior accuracy performance compared to all other data augmentation methods across both datasets. For the FSDD dataset, the proposed method showed an absolute improvement of nearly 3% over the baseline, while for the UrbanSound8K dataset, it demonstrated an absolute improvement of approximately 2.30%. Overall, our proposed method achieved the best accuracy performance among all the methods employed.

6 Conclusion

This paper introduces AudRandAug, a novel data augmentation technique specifically designed for audio data. AudRandAug selects data augmentation policies from a dedicated audio search space and demonstrates remarkable performance improvements compared to the baseline. Through extensive experiments on FSDD and UrbanSound8K datasets, using various models, AudRandAug consistently outperforms other data augmentation methods. The results validate the effectiveness and potential of AudRandAug in enhancing the performance of audio-related models. By addressing the specific needs of audio data, this research contributes to the advancement of audio tasks within the computer vision field. In future, AudRandAug can be used as a powerful technique for audio data augmentation, demonstrating significant accuracy improvements. This work opens up possibilities for further research and development of tailored data augmentation methods to optimize audio-related applications.

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References

- [BSG, 2020] (2020). Search for optimal data augmentation policy for environmental sound classification with deep neural networks. *Journal of Broadcast Engineering*, 6(6).
- [Aleem et al., 2022] Aleem, S., Kumar, T., Little, S., Bendeche, M., Brennan, R., and McGuinness, K. (2022). Random data augmentation based enhancement: a generalized enhancement approach for medical datasets. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.00824*.
- [Aytar et al., 2016] Aytar, Y., Vondrick, C., and Torralba, A. (2016). Soundnet: Learning sound representations from unlabeled video. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 29.
- [Chachada and Kuo, 2014] Chachada, S. and Kuo, C.-C. J. (2014). Environmental sound recognition: A survey. *APSIPA Transactions on Signal and Information Processing*, 3.
- [Chandio et al., 2021] Chandio, A., Shen, Y., Bendeche, M., Inayat, I., and Kumar, T. (2021). Audd: audio urdu digits dataset for automatic audio urdu digit recognition. *Applied Sciences*, 11(19):8842.

- [Choi et al., 2017] Choi, K., Fazekas, G., Sandler, M., and Cho, K. (2017). Convolutional recurrent neural networks for music classification. In *2017 IEEE International conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (ICASSP)*, pages 2392–2396. IEEE.
- [Cubuk et al., 2020] Cubuk, E. D., Zoph, B., Shlens, J., and Le, Q. V. (2020). Randaugment: Practical automated data augmentation with a reduced search space. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition workshops*, pages 702–703.
- [Dandashi and AlJaam, 2017] Dandashi, A. and AlJaam, J. (2017). A survey on audio content-based classification. In *2017 International conference on computational science and computational intelligence (CSCI)*, pages 408–413. IEEE.
- [Demir et al., 2020] Demir, F., Abdullah, D. A., and Sengur, A. (2020). A new deep cnn model for environmental sound classification. *IEEE Access*, 8:66529–66537.
- [Dong, 2018] Dong, M. (2018). Convolutional neural network achieves human-level accuracy in music genre classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.09697*.
- [Fu et al., 2010] Fu, Z., Lu, G., Ting, K. M., and Zhang, D. (2010). A survey of audio-based music classification and annotation. *IEEE transactions on multimedia*, 13(2):303–319.
- [Fujiyoshi et al., 2019] Fujiyoshi, H., Hirakawa, T., and Yamashita, T. (2019). Deep learning-based image recognition for autonomous driving. *IATSS research*, 43(4):244–252.
- [Guzhov et al., 2021] Guzhov, A., Raue, F., Hees, J., and Dengel, A. (2021). Esresnet: Environmental sound classification based on visual domain models. In *2020 25th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)*, pages 4933–4940. IEEE.
- [Hershey et al., 2017] Hershey, S., Chaudhuri, S., Ellis, D. P., Gemmeke, J. F., Jansen, A., Moore, R. C., Plakal, M., Platt, D., Saurous, R. A., Seybold, B., et al. (2017). Cnn architectures for large-scale audio classification. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 131–135. IEEE.
- [Hirschberg and Manning, 2015] Hirschberg, J. and Manning, C. D. (2015). Advances in natural language processing. *Science*, 349(6245):261–266.
- [Jackson, 2016] Jackson, Z. (2016). Free spoken digit dataset (fsdd). Retrieved February, 1:2020.
- [Jain et al., 2021] Jain, A., Samala, P. R., Mittal, D., Jyoti, P., and Singh, M. (2021). Spliceout: A simple and efficient audio augmentation method. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.00046*.
- [Kim et al., 2021] Kim, G., Han, D. K., and Ko, H. (2021). Specmix: A mixed sample data augmentation method for training with time-frequency domain features. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.03020*.
- [Ko et al., 2015] Ko, T., Peddinti, V., Povey, D., and Khudanpur, S. (2015). Audio augmentation for speech recognition. In *Sixteenth annual conference of the international speech communication association*.
- [Kumar et al., 2023a] Kumar, T., Mileo, A., Brennan, R., and Bendeche, M. (2023a). Rsmlda: Random slices mixing data augmentation. *Applied Sciences*, 13(3):1711.
- [Kumar et al., 2021a] Kumar, T., Park, J., Ali, M. S., Uddin, A., and Bae, S.-H. (2021a). Class specific autoencoders enhance sample diversity. *Journal of Broadcast Engineering*, 26(7):844–854.
- [Kumar et al., 2021b] Kumar, T., Park, J., Ali, M. S., Uddin, A. S., Ko, J. H., and Bae, S.-H. (2021b). Binary-classifiers-enabled filters for semi-supervised learning. *IEEE Access*, 9:167663–167673.

- [Kumar et al., 2020] Kumar, T., Park, J., and Bae, S.-H. (2020). Intra-class random erasing (icre) augmentation for audio classification. In *Proceedings Of The Korean Society Of Broadcast Engineers Conference*, pages 244–247. The Korean Institute of Broadcast and Media Engineers.
- [Kumar et al., 2023b] Kumar, T., Turab, M., Raj, K., Mileo, A., Brennan, R., and Bendeche, M. (2023b). Advanced data augmentation approaches: A comprehensive survey and future directions. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.02830*.
- [Lee et al., 2017a] Lee, J., Kim, T., Park, J., and Nam, J. (2017a). Raw waveform-based audio classification using sample-level cnn architectures. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1712.00866*.
- [Lee et al., 2017b] Lee, J., Park, J., Kim, K. L., and Nam, J. (2017b). Sample-level deep convolutional neural networks for music auto-tagging using raw waveforms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1703.01789*.
- [Li et al., 2019] Li, X., Chebiyyam, V., and Kirchhoff, K. (2019). Multi-stream network with temporal attention for environmental sound classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.08608*.
- [Liu et al., 1998] Liu, Z., Wang, Y., and Chen, T. (1998). Audio feature extraction and analysis for scene segmentation and classification. *Journal of VLSI signal processing systems for signal, image and video technology*, 20(1):61–79.
- [Nanni et al., 2020] Nanni, L., Maguolo, G., and Paci, M. (2020). Data augmentation approaches for improving animal audio classification. *Ecological Informatics*, 57:101084.
- [Oord et al., 2016] Oord, A. v. d., Dieleman, S., Zen, H., Simonyan, K., Vinyals, O., Graves, A., Kalchbrenner, N., Senior, A., and Kavukcuoglu, K. (2016). Wavenet: A generative model for raw audio. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.03499*.
- [Palanisamy et al., 2020] Palanisamy, K., Singhanian, D., and Yao, A. (2020). Rethinking cnn models for audio classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.11154*.
- [Park et al., 2020] Park, J., Kumar, T., and Bae, S.-H. (2020). Search for optimal data augmentation policy for environmental sound classification with deep neural networks. *Journal of Broadcast Engineering*, 25(6):854–860.
- [Ranjbarzadeh et al., 2023] Ranjbarzadeh, R., Jafarzadeh Ghouschi, S., Tataei Sarshar, N., Tirkolae, E. B., Ali, S. S., Kumar, T., and Bendeche, M. (2023). Me-ccnn: Multi-encoded images and a cascade convolutional neural network for breast tumor segmentation and recognition. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, pages 1–38.
- [Roberts et al., 2018] Roberts, A., Engel, J., Raffel, C., Hawthorne, C., and Eck, D. (2018). A hierarchical latent vector model for learning long-term structure in music. In *International conference on machine learning*, pages 4364–4373. PMLR.
- [Salamon and Bello, 2017] Salamon, J. and Bello, J. P. (2017). Deep convolutional neural networks and data augmentation for environmental sound classification. *IEEE Signal processing letters*, 24(3):279–283.
- [Salamon et al., 2014] Salamon, J., Jacoby, C., and Bello, J. P. (2014). A dataset and taxonomy for urban sound research. In *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, MM '14, page 1041–1044, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [Su et al., 2019] Su, Y., Zhang, K., Wang, J., and Madani, K. (2019). Environment sound classification using a two-stream cnn based on decision-level fusion. *Sensors*, 19(7):1733.

- [Tokozume and Harada, 2017] Tokozume, Y. and Harada, T. (2017). Learning environmental sounds with end-to-end convolutional neural network. In *2017 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (ICASSP)*, pages 2721–2725. IEEE.
- [Torfi et al., 2020] Torfi, A., Shirvani, R. A., Keneshloo, Y., Tavaf, N., and Fox, E. A. (2020). Natural language processing advancements by deep learning: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.01200*.
- [Turab et al., 2022] Turab, M., Kumar, T., Bendeche, M., and Saber, T. (2022). Investigating multi-feature selection and ensembling for audio classification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.07511*.
- [Wu and Chen, 2015] Wu, M. and Chen, L. (2015). Image recognition based on deep learning. In *2015 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC)*, pages 542–546. IEEE.
- [Zhang et al., 2016] Zhang, W., Lei, W., Xu, X., and Xing, X. (2016). Improved music genre classification with convolutional neural networks. In *Interspeech*, pages 3304–3308.